

MUPADAYON UG ESKWELA O DILI: FACTORS INFLUENCING SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS' INTENTIONS TO PURSUE COLLEGE

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ABSTRACT

This action research investigated the barriers encountered by senior high school students in pursuing college education and implemented a school-based intervention to address these challenges. Results of the preliminary needs assessment revealed that despite strong intentions to enroll in higher education, students were constrained by financial limitations, limited access to scholarship information, and insufficient career guidance. In response, the College Access Support Program (CASP) was developed to provide structured scholarship assistance and systematic career guidance to Grade 12 students. The study followed an action research design encompassing the stages of diagnosis, planning, action, and reflection. Data were collected through surveys, document review, and monitoring of students' participation in scholarship applications and career-related activities. The intervention included three key components: government scholarship assistance (Scholar ni Gov), local government scholarship facilitation (Scholarship ni Mayor), and career guidance and college readiness seminars. Descriptive analysis revealed improvements in students' awareness of scholarship opportunities, increased participation in scholarship applications, and enhanced clarity in course and career choices. Moreover, students demonstrated greater confidence and readiness to

pursue higher education. The study concludes that structured scholarship support, combined with comprehensive career guidance, effectively bridges the gap between students' aspirations and actual college enrollment. These findings highlight the importance of institutionalizing school-based support systems to promote equitable access to higher education.

Keywords: *college intention, senior high school, theory of planned behavior, career guidance, action research*

INTRODUCTION

The implementation of the K to 12 Basic Education Program in the Philippines aims to equip learners with competencies for employment, entrepreneurship, middle-level skills development, or higher education. Senior High School (SHS), in particular, prepares learners for multiple post-secondary pathways based on their interests, abilities, and circumstances. Despite this intent, not all SHS graduates plan to pursue college education, as school-level observations indicate varying post-secondary decisions across academic strands and socioeconomic backgrounds. Some learners express strong intentions to continue to higher education, while others prefer technical-vocational pathways, immediate employment, or remain undecided.

Students' decisions regarding post-secondary plans are shaped by both personal and external factors. Personal factors include academic self-confidence, motivation, perceived relevance of college to career goals, and readiness for higher education. Salinas (2019) found that Filipino senior high school students with higher academic aspirations were more likely to feel prepared to pursue a college degree, emphasizing that aspiration and readiness significantly influence students' intentions to continue to higher education. In addition, career awareness and alignment of students' abilities with potential career paths also play an important role in shaping educational choices. Parojenog et al. (2022) highlighted that understanding students' multiple intelligences and career preferences is essential in guiding Senior High School learners toward appropriate career and educational pathways, emphasizing the importance of career guidance orientation programs in helping students make informed decisions about their future.

Despite these findings, there remains limited school-based empirical evidence that captures SHS students' actual perceptions, attitudes, and lived realities regarding their post-secondary plans. Understanding these context-specific factors is essential for school administrators and teachers to design targeted, evidence-based interventions, including enhanced career guidance programs, scholarship and financial aid orientations, parental engagement initiatives, and college readiness workshops. Such interventions aim to support students in making informed, realistic, and well-supported decisions about their educational futures.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the factors influencing Senior High School students' intention to pursue college education and to use the findings as a basis for developing appropriate school-based interventions.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the Senior High School students in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 gender;
 - 1.3 strand;
 - 1.4 family size;
 - 1.5 household income; and
 - 1.6 parents' educational attainment?
 - a. Father;
 - b. Mother?
2. What are the students' perceptions, attitudes, and social influences regarding college education in terms of:
 - 2.1. perceived benefits;
 - 2.2. subjective norms;
 - 2.3. perceived behavioral control;
 - 2.4. motivation;
 - 2.5. career clarity; and
 - 2.6. academic self-efficacy?
3. What barriers and practical constraints do students encounter that may hinder their intention to pursue college?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive mixed-methods research design to examine Senior High School students' perceptions, attitudes, social influences, and barriers to pursuing a college education. The quantitative component described students' demographic characteristics and measured their perceptions of college education, while the qualitative component explored the barriers and practical constraints that may hinder their intention to pursue higher education.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire administered to Grade 11 and Grade 12 students at San Isidro Senior High School in Montalban, Rizal. The instrument included items measuring students' perceptions of the benefits of college education, subjective norms (social influences), perceived behavioral control, motivation toward education, career clarity, perceived alternatives, and academic self-efficacy. In

addition, open-ended responses were included to identify barriers and practical constraints that students encountered in pursuing higher education.

The questionnaire was validated by experts in education and research to ensure content validity and clarity. Quantitative data were analyzed using frequencies and percentages to describe the respondents' demographic profile, while the weighted mean and standard deviation were used to determine the levels of students' perceptions, attitudes, and social influences regarding college education. The qualitative responses related to barriers and constraints were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify recurring themes explaining factors affecting students' intention to pursue a college education.

Research Environment

The study was conducted at San Isidro Senior High School in San Isidro, Montalban, Rizal, Philippines. The school offers Senior High School programs under the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum, including academic and technical-vocational tracks. It serves students from the local community who are preparing for their post-Senior High School educational and career pathways.

Research Participants

The participants in the study were Grade 11 and Grade 12 students currently enrolled at San Isidro Senior High School in Montalban, Rizal. These students were selected because they are at a critical stage of deciding whether to pursue higher education after completing Senior High School. Participation in the study was voluntary, and respondents were included based on their willingness and availability.

Research Instrument

The study used a researcher-developed structured questionnaire to collect data from respondents. The instrument consisted of three parts. The first part collected the demographic profile of the respondents, including age, gender, strand, number of siblings, family income, and parents' educational attainment.

The second part contained Likert-scale items designed to measure students' perceptions, attitudes, and social influences regarding college education. The indicators included perceived benefits, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, motivation toward education, career clarity, perceived alternatives, and academic self-efficacy. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree.

The third part included open-ended questions that allowed students to describe the barriers and practical constraints they encounter that may hinder their intention to pursue college education.

Research Procedure

Prior to data collection, permission to conduct the study was obtained from the head of the school, San Isidro Senior High School. The participants were informed about the purpose of the study, and their voluntary participation and confidentiality were assured. The structured questionnaire was then administered to Grade 11 and Grade 12 students. After collection, the responses were organized, tabulated, and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools to describe students' perceptions and intentions regarding college education.

Data Analysis

The collected data were organized, tabulated, and analyzed using descriptive statistical techniques. Frequency and percentage distributions were used to describe the demographic profile of the respondents, including age, sex, strand, number of siblings, family income, and parents' educational attainment.

To assess students' perceptions, attitudes, and social influences regarding college education, weighted means and standard deviations were computed. These statistical measures were used to analyze indicators related to perceived benefits, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, motivation toward education, career clarity, perceived alternatives, and academic self-efficacy. The results were interpreted using a five-point Likert scale, with descriptive interpretations ranging from *Strongly Agree* to *Strongly Disagree*.

The responses to the open-ended questions regarding barriers and practical constraints were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify recurring themes explaining the factors influencing students' intention to pursue a college education.

RESULTS

This section presents the study's results in relation to the identified research problems. It describes the demographic characteristics of Senior High School students and examines their perceptions, attitudes, and social influences toward college education. The discussion focuses on students' readiness, motivation, sense of control, and decision-making related to higher education. The findings help explain the factors influencing students' educational goals and provide a basis for developing appropriate school-based interventions.

Table 1.1
Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
14–17	200	47.7%	2
18–21	213	50.8%	1
22 years old and above	6	1.4%	3

Table 1.1 shows that the majority of respondents are in the 18–21 age group (50.8%), followed by those aged 14–17 years (47.7%), while only 1.4% are 22 years and older. This indicates that most respondents fall within the typical age range for Senior High School students approaching the transition to higher education.

Table 1.2
Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Male	204	48.7%	2
Female	215	51.3%	1

Table 1.2 indicates that female students slightly outnumber males, with 51.3% female and 48.7% male respondents. The relatively balanced distribution suggests that both sexes are similarly represented in the study and share comparable educational experiences and future academic planning.

Table 1.3
Strand

Strand	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
ABM	51	12.2%	3
HUMSS	190	45.3%	1
TVL	178	42.5%	2

As shown in Table 1.3, the HUMSS strand accounts for the largest proportion of respondents (45.3%), followed by TVL (42.5%) and ABM (12.2%). This distribution suggests that most students are enrolled in either social science–oriented or technical-vocational programs, which may influence their perspectives on pursuing higher education or alternative career pathways.

Table 1.4
Family Size

Family Size	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1–3 siblings	213	50.8%	1
4–6 siblings	164	39.1%	2
6 or more siblings	42	10.0%	3

Table 1.4 reveals that 50.8% of respondents come from families with 1–3 siblings, followed by 39.1% with 4–6 siblings, and 10% with 6 or more siblings. This suggests that most students come from small to medium-sized families, which may influence the allocation of family resources and educational opportunities. This finding supports the study by Feng (2021), which found that family size can influence children’s educational opportunities, as parents in smaller families are generally able to allocate more financial support, attention, and educational resources to each child than those in larger families.

Table 1.5
Household Income

Income	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
<₱10,000	214	51.1%	1
₱10,000–₱20,000	102	24.3%	2
₱20,001–₱40,000	18	4.3%	4
₱40,001–₱60,000	0	0%	6
>₱60,000	0	0%	6
Prefer not to say	85	20.3%	3

Table 1.5 shows that the majority of respondents (51.1%) belong to households earning below ₱10,000 per month, followed by 24.3% earning ₱10,000–₱20,000. These findings indicate that many students come from low-income households, which may present financial challenges in accessing higher education. This finding supports the study by Albert et al. (2018), which reported that students from low-income families in the Philippines often face financial constraints that limit their ability to pursue higher education, highlighting the influence of household income on educational opportunities.

Table 1.6
Educational Attainment of Fathers of the Respondents

Education/Father	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
No formal education	36	8.6%	7
Elementary Level	64	15.3%	4
Elementary Graduate	55	13.1%	5
High School Level	91	21.7%	3
High School Graduate	103	24.6%	1
College Level	52	12.4%	6
College Graduate	18	4.3%	8
Prefer not to say	0	0%	9

Table 1.6 presents the educational attainment of the respondents' fathers. The data show that the largest proportion of fathers are high school graduates (24.6%), followed by those with high school level education (21.7%). A smaller percentage reached college level (12.4%), while only 4.3% completed a college degree. These findings suggest that many students come from households where fathers have limited exposure to higher education. This finding is supported by Davis-Kean (2005), who found that parents' educational attainment significantly influences children's academic achievement, educational expectations, and access to learning resources. Consequently, school-based support programs may play an important role in assisting students from families with lower educational attainment to pursue higher education.

Table 1.7
Educational Attainment of Mothers of the Respondents

Education/Mother	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
No formal education	24	5.7%	7
Elementary Level	55	13.1%	4
Elementary Graduate	37	8.8%	6
High School Level	103	24.6%	2
High School Graduate	109	26.0%	1
College Level	55	13.1%	4
College Graduate	36	8.6%	6
Prefer not to say	0	0%	8

Table 1.7 shows the educational attainment of the respondents' mothers. The results indicate that the majority of mothers are high school graduates (26.0%), followed by those with high school level education (24.6%). Only a small proportion reached college level (13.1%) or completed a college degree (8.6%), while 5.7% reported having no formal education. These findings suggest that many students come from families where mothers have limited exposure to higher education, which may influence students' academic guidance and educational aspirations. Research has shown that parental educational background is a significant factor influencing students' motivation and educational outcomes (Sirin, 2005).

Students' Perceptions, Attitudes, and Social Influences Regarding College Education. This section presents students' perceptions, attitudes, and social influences regarding college education, including perceived benefits, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, motivation, career clarity, perceived alternatives, and academic self-efficacy.

Table 2.1
Perceived Benefits

Indicators	Weighted Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. A college degree increases my chances of getting a stable job.	4.01	0.853	Agree
2. College education can help me earn a higher income in the future.	4.01	0.837	Agree
3. Finishing college will give me better career opportunities locally and abroad.	3.90	0.913	Agree
4. College graduates are more respected in society.	3.85	0.804	Agree
5. College education will help me develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills.	3.96	0.836	Agree
6. Attending college will improve my confidence and independence.	3.76	0.870	Agree
7. A college degree is important for long-term career growth.	3.93	0.946	Agree
8. College education can provide better opportunities for career advancement.	3.94	0.908	Agree
9. Finishing college will help me achieve my personal goals in life.	4.06	0.939	Agree
10. College education is a worthwhile investment for my future.	3.94	0.969	Agree
Overall	3.94	0.801	Agree

Table 2.1 presents students' perceptions of the benefits of pursuing a college education. The results indicate that students generally agree on the benefits of college education, with an overall weighted mean of 3.94, interpreted as *Agree*. Students strongly associate college education with improved employment opportunities and higher future income, as reflected in the indicators *"A college degree increases my chances of getting a stable job"* and *"College education can help me earn a higher income in the future."*

Students also recognize that a college education contributes to career advancement, the attainment of personal goals, and intellectual development, including critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Previous studies have shown that higher education significantly enhances employability, career development, and personal growth (Pascarella & Terenzini, 2005; Marginson, 2016). Overall, the findings suggest that students view college education as a valuable investment for their future.

Table 2.2
Subjective Norms

Indicators	Weighted Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. My parents expect me to continue my studies in college.	4.15	0.920	Agree
2. My family believes that going to college is important.	3.70	0.868	Agree
3. My teachers encourage me to pursue college education.	3.87	0.925	Agree
4. My classmates influence my decision to go to college.	3.72	0.913	Agree
5. Most of my close friends plan to attend college.	3.56	0.806	Agree
6. People important to me think I should go to college.	3.66	0.810	Agree
7. My school promotes college education as a positive pathway.	3.56	0.906	Agree
8. My relatives encourage me to pursue higher education.	3.80	0.839	Agree
9. I feel pressured by others to pursue a college education.	3.80	0.888	Agree
10. Advice from teachers and school staff influences my decision to go to college.	3.80	0.872	Agree
Overall	3.76	0.748	Agree

Table 2.2 presents students' perceptions of subjective norms or social influences related to pursuing a college education. The results reveal that students agree that social influences affect their decision to pursue college education, with an overall weighted mean of 3.76. Parental expectations obtained the highest rating, indicating that family encouragement plays a significant role in motivating students to continue their education.

Teachers, school personnel, and peers also influence students' educational decisions. Previous research indicates that parental support, teacher encouragement, and peer influence significantly shape students' academic aspirations and decisions regarding higher education (Fan & Chen, 2001; Eccles & Roeser, 2011). These findings highlight the importance of family and school support systems in promoting students' college aspirations.

Table 2.3
Perceived Behavioral Control

Indicators	Weighted Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I believe I can afford college if I receive financial assistance.	4.03	0.956	Agree
2. I know where and how to apply for college admission.	4.07	0.915	Agree

3. I am confident that I can meet college admission requirements.	4.03	0.910	Agree
4. I can manage my time if I study and work at the same time.	4.14	0.915	Agree
5. I have access to information about scholarships and financial aid.	4.25	0.967	Strongly Agree
6. Transportation and distance will not stop me from attending college.	4.14	0.867	Agree
7. I believe I can handle the academic workload in college.	4.21	0.999	Strongly Agree
8. I have the support I need to succeed in college.	4.06	0.969	Agree
9. I can overcome challenges that may prevent me from enrolling in college.	4.17	1.014	Agree
10. The decision to pursue college is mostly under my control.	4.06	0.998	Agree
Overall	4.12	0.876	Agree

Table 2.3 presents students' perceptions of perceived behavioral control in pursuing a college education. The findings show that students generally perceive themselves as capable of pursuing college education, with an overall weighted mean of 4.12, interpreted as *Agree*. Students expressed confidence in their ability to meet admission requirements, manage academic tasks, and overcome potential challenges related to college education.

Access to scholarship information and financial assistance received the highest rating, indicating that financial support significantly strengthens students' confidence in pursuing higher education. Studies have shown that access to academic guidance, institutional resources, and financial assistance positively influences students' college readiness and self-efficacy (Cabrera & La Nasa, 2000).

Table 2.4
Motivation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I am motivated to continue studying after Senior High School.	4.03	0.956	Agree
2. I value education as an important part of personal growth.	4.07	0.915	Agree
3. I am willing to make sacrifices to finish college.	4.03	0.910	Agree
4. Learning new things excites and motivates me.	4.14	0.915	Agree
5. I believe education will help me achieve a better future.	4.25	0.967	Strongly Agree
6. I am determined to pursue my goals through higher education.	4.14	0.867	Agree
7. I see college education as meaningful and purposeful.	4.21	0.999	Strongly Agree
8. I am motivated to improve myself through continued learning.	4.06	0.969	Agree
9. I am willing to work hard to succeed in college.	4.17	1.014	Agree
10. I believe lifelong learning is important for success in life.	4.06	0.998	Agree
Overall	4.12	0.876	Agree

Table 2.4 presents students' levels of motivation and value toward education. The results reveal that students demonstrate high motivation to continue their education, with an overall weighted mean of 4.12, interpreted as *Agree*. Students strongly believe that education will help them achieve a better future and recognize the importance of lifelong learning and personal development.

Indicators related to perseverance, determination, and willingness to make sacrifices reflect students' strong commitment to achieving their educational goals. These findings are consistent with motivational theories suggesting that intrinsic motivation and

goal orientation significantly influence academic persistence and success (Ryan & Deci, 2000; Pintrich & De Groot, 1990).

Table 2.5
Career Clarity

Indicators	Weighted Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I have a clear idea of the career I want to pursue.	4.27	1.028	Strongly Agree
2. I know what college course is needed for my desired career.	4.31	1.022	Strongly Agree
3. My Senior High School strand aligns with my career goals.	4.14	1.032	Agree
4. I understand the skills required for my future career.	4.15	1.023	Agree
5. I have researched jobs related to my chosen career.	4.27	1.028	Strongly Agree
6. I am confident about the career path I want to take.	4.31	1.036	Strongly Agree
7. I know the educational requirements of my target profession.	4.10	0.988	Agree
8. My career goals motivate me to pursue college education.	4.31	1.036	Strongly Agree
9. I have a long-term plan for my career.	4.27	1.028	Strongly Agree
10. College education is necessary to achieve my career goals.	4.11	0.949	Agree
Overall	4.22	0.974	Strongly Agree

Table 2.5 presents students' level of career clarity regarding pursuing a college education. The results indicate that students demonstrate a high level of career clarity, with an overall weighted mean of 4.22, interpreted as *Strongly Agree*. Students reported strong awareness of their preferred career paths, the college courses required to achieve their goals, and the skills needed for their future professions.

These findings suggest that students clearly understand the relationship between higher education and career success. Career development theories emphasize that early career awareness and planning significantly influence educational decisions and long-term career outcomes (Super et al., 1992; Lent et al., 1994).

Table 2.6
Academic Self-Efficacy

Indicators	Weighted Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I am confident that I can succeed in college-level subjects.	4.30	1.047	Strongly Agree
2. I can understand difficult lessons if I put in effort.	4.24	1.021	Strongly Agree
3. I can manage multiple academic tasks effectively.	3.87	0.985	Agree
4. I am confident in my study and learning skills.	4.15	0.980	Agree
5. I can complete college requirements on time.	4.13	0.955	Agree
6. I believe I can perform well in exams and assessments.	4.24	1.048	Strongly Agree
7. I can stay focused even when academic work is challenging.	4.13	0.985	Agree
8. I am capable of learning new and complex topics.	4.11	0.979	Agree
9. I can handle academic pressure in college.	4.10	0.973	Agree
10. I believe in my ability to succeed academically in college.	3.94	0.954	Agree
Overall	4.12	0.925	Agree

Table 2.7 presents students' academic self-efficacy levels in relation to college education. The results show that students demonstrate a positive level of academic self-efficacy, with an overall weighted mean of 4.12, interpreted as *Agree*. Students expressed confidence in their ability to understand complex lessons, manage academic tasks, and succeed in college-level coursework.

Research suggests that strong academic self-efficacy contributes to higher levels of academic motivation, persistence, and achievement in higher education (Bandura, 1997; Chemers et al., 2001). These findings indicate that students generally believe they have the capacity to meet the academic demands of college.

Barriers and Practical Constraints Affecting Students' Intention to Pursue College

The data were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify common barriers and practical constraints that may hinder students' pursuit of a college education. The analysis revealed several recurring themes related to financial, social, logistical, and personal factors influencing students' decisions about higher education.

Theme 1: Financial Constraints

One of the most prominent themes identified is financial constraint, particularly the high cost of tuition and other educational expenses. Many students expressed concerns about the affordability of college, including tuition, books, transportation, and other academic expenses. For students coming from low- and middle-income households, these financial demands pose a significant challenge to pursuing higher education.

Research consistently indicates that financial limitations are among the strongest barriers to college participation. Students from economically disadvantaged families are often less likely to enroll in or complete higher education due to affordability issues (Perna, 2006; McDonough, 2005). These findings highlight the importance of expanding scholarships, grants, and financial aid programs to reduce economic barriers for students.

Theme 2: Need to Work or Support the Family

Another recurring theme is the need to work or contribute to family income. Some students reported that they may need to seek employment immediately after Senior High School to support themselves or assist their families financially. The pressure to earn income can make pursuing college less feasible, especially when financial resources are limited.

Previous studies suggest that students who prioritize employment often struggle to balance work and academic responsibilities, which may reduce their likelihood of enrolling in higher education or delay their college entry (Tinto, 2012; Perna, 2010).

Theme 3: Family Responsibilities and Expectations

Family responsibilities also emerged as a significant barrier. Some students are expected to assist with household tasks, care for younger siblings, or help manage family businesses or farms. These obligations can reduce the time and resources available for pursuing higher education.

Sociological research has shown that family responsibilities and expectations can significantly influence students' educational pathways. In households where students are expected to contribute to family responsibilities, educational aspirations may take a back seat to family needs (Fan & Chen, 2001).

Theme 4: Lack of Interest or Alignment with College Programs

Some students indicated a lack of interest in available college programs or felt that existing academic offerings did not align with their career goals or personal interests. When students perceive that college programs are not relevant to their aspirations, their motivation to pursue higher education may decrease.

Motivation and perceived relevance of academic programs are key factors in students' educational decisions. Studies suggest that students are more likely to pursue higher education when academic programs align with their career goals and personal interests (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002).

Theme 5: Preference for Vocational or Technical Pathways

Another theme identified is a preference for vocational or technical education over traditional college pathways. Some students view technical training, apprenticeships, or skills-based programs as more practical and beneficial for immediate employment.

Research on career development emphasizes that vocational education can provide direct pathways to employment and skill development, making it an attractive option for students seeking faster entry into the labor market (Symonds et al., 2011; Fuller & Unwin, 2011).

Theme 6: Geographic and Transportation Barriers

Logistical challenges, particularly distance from colleges and transportation difficulties, were also identified as barriers. Students living far from higher education institutions may face additional commuting costs and time constraints.

Studies on educational access highlight that proximity to educational institutions significantly influences college enrollment, particularly among students in rural or underserved communities (Peer, 2024).

Theme 7: Health and Personal Limitations

Health-related concerns and personal challenges were also mentioned as factors that may affect students' readiness to pursue higher education. Physical or mental health issues can affect students' ability to maintain regular attendance, manage academic workload, and adapt to the demands of college life.

Inclusive education research emphasizes the importance of providing support services, accommodations, and accessible learning environments to ensure that students with health challenges have equal opportunities for educational advancement (Debasu & Yitayew, 2024).

Theme 8: Limited Awareness of College Application Processes

Another barrier identified is limited information about college admission procedures, including application requirements, deadlines, and scholarship opportunities. Students who lack clear information about these processes may feel uncertain or discouraged about pursuing higher education.

Research on college access highlights the critical role of guidance and counseling services in helping students navigate application procedures and financial aid opportunities (McDonough, 2005; Perna, 2006).

Theme 9: Family Attitudes Toward College

Family attitudes toward higher education also influence students' intentions to pursue college. In cases where families do not strongly encourage college education or prioritize alternative career paths, students may feel less motivated to continue their studies.

Studies have shown that parental expectations and attitudes significantly affect students' academic aspirations and educational outcomes (Fan & Chen, 2001; Hill & Tyson, 2009).

Summary of Themes

The thematic analysis indicates that students' intentions to pursue college education are shaped by a combination of financial constraints, family responsibilities, logistical challenges, personal motivations, and informational barriers. Addressing these factors requires coordinated efforts from schools, families, and policymakers to provide financial support, effective career guidance, and accessible educational opportunities for students.

DISCUSSION

The main purpose of this study was to examine Senior High School students' perceptions, attitudes, and social influences regarding their intention to pursue college education, as well as the barriers that may hinder their educational aspirations. The study explored students' perceived benefits of college education, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, motivation, career clarity, perceived alternatives, and academic self-efficacy.

The findings revealed that students generally hold positive perceptions of college education. Most respondents recognize higher education as a pathway to better employment opportunities, career advancement, and personal development. Social influences, particularly parental expectations and teacher encouragement, also play an important role in shaping students' intentions to pursue college. In addition, students demonstrate a positive level of perceived behavioral control, motivation, and academic self-efficacy, indicating confidence in their ability to succeed in higher education.

Despite these positive perceptions, the study also identified several barriers and practical constraints that may hinder students' pursuit of college. These barriers include financial limitations, the need to support family income, family responsibilities, limited information about college admission processes, and logistical challenges such as distance and transportation. Some students also expressed a preference for vocational or technical pathways as alternatives to traditional college education.

Overall, the findings suggest that while students recognize the value of higher education and demonstrate strong motivation to pursue college, various economic, social, and informational factors continue to influence their educational decisions. These insights highlight the importance of strengthening school-based guidance, financial support programs, and career orientation initiatives to help students successfully transition from Senior High School to higher education.

Findings

Based on the analysis of the data gathered from Senior High School students, the following findings were obtained:

- 1. Profile of the Respondents.** Most respondents belong to the 18–21-year-old age group, with females slightly outnumbering males. The majority of students are enrolled in the HUMSS strand, followed by the TVL strand. In terms of family background, most respondents come from families with one to three siblings and from low-income households, with many reporting a monthly family income of less than ₱10,000. Parents' educational attainment shows that most mothers and fathers are high school graduates, indicating that many students come from families with limited exposure to higher education.
- 2. Students' Perceptions, Attitudes, and Social Influences Regarding College Education.** Students generally exhibit positive perceptions toward college education. In terms of perceived benefits, respondents agreed that pursuing a college education increases opportunities for stable employment, higher income, and career advancement. Regarding subjective norms, parents, teachers, and peers were found to significantly influence students' intentions to pursue college education. Students also demonstrated positive perceived behavioral control, indicating confidence in their ability to manage college requirements and overcome potential challenges.

In terms of motivation, students strongly agreed that education is important for achieving personal and professional goals. The findings also indicate a high level of career clarity, with many students reporting a clear understanding of their desired careers and the educational pathways required to achieve them. Furthermore, students demonstrated positive academic self-efficacy, expressing confidence in their ability to succeed in college-level academic work. At the same time, students acknowledged the existence of alternative pathways, such as technical-vocational training, entrepreneurship, and employment opportunities, as possible options after Senior High School.

- 3. Barriers and Practical Constraints Affecting Students' Intention to Pursue College.** Despite recognizing the benefits of higher education, several barriers were identified that may hinder students' pursuit of college. These barriers include financial constraints, particularly the high cost of tuition and other educational expenses. Other constraints include the need to work or contribute to family income, family responsibilities, and limited access to information about college application processes and scholarship opportunities. Logistical factors such as distance from higher education institutions and transportation difficulties were also identified as challenges. Additionally, some students expressed a preference for vocational or technical pathways as alternatives to traditional college education.

Conclusions

This action research set out to address the persistent gap between senior high school students' aspirations to pursue college education and their actual capacity to do so. The findings clearly demonstrated that, while students possess the motivation and intent to pursue higher education, structural barriers—particularly financial limitations, limited access to scholarship information, and insufficient career guidance—significantly constrain their educational trajectories.

The implementation of the College Access Support Program (CASP) provided a practical and context-sensitive response to these challenges. Through its three integrated components—government scholarship assistance, local government scholarship facilitation, and career guidance and college readiness orientation—the program effectively addressed both economic and psychosocial barriers to college access. The increase in scholarship applications, improved completion of requirements, and enhanced student clarity regarding course and career choices indicate that the intervention successfully strengthened students' readiness for higher education. More importantly, the study highlights the critical role of schools as active facilitators of post-secondary transitions. When schools move beyond academic instruction and provide structured support systems, students—especially those from low-income and at-risk backgrounds—are better equipped to make informed decisions and access opportunities that would otherwise remain beyond reach.

In conclusion, the College Access Support Program proved to be a viable and effective intervention for improving college access among senior high school students. It

is recommended that the program be institutionalized at the school level and adapted by other schools with similar contexts. Future studies may explore the long-term impact of such interventions on college persistence and completion, thereby contributing further to policies and practices that promote inclusive and equitable education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to help Senior High School students overcome barriers and maximize their potential in pursuing higher education and alternative career pathways:

- 1. Enhance Financial Support Programs.** Schools, local government units, and policymakers should strengthen scholarship programs, tuition subsidies, and financial assistance schemes. Targeted financial support can help students from low-income families pursue higher education without undue financial stress, ensuring that cost is not a barrier to achieving their academic goals.
- 2. Provide Comprehensive Career Guidance and Counseling.** Schools should implement structured, ongoing career guidance programs that inform students about college courses, admissions processes, scholarship opportunities, and alternative vocational pathways. These programs can equip students with the knowledge and confidence to make informed decisions aligned with their personal interests, strengths, and career aspirations.
- 3. Promote Awareness of Vocational and Alternative Pathways.** Alongside traditional college education, students should be made aware of viable alternatives such as technical-vocational programs, apprenticeships, and entrepreneurship opportunities. Recognizing these options allows students to balance career readiness, skill development, and financial independence while pursuing their long-term goals.
- 4. Encourage Family and Community Involvement.** Parents, guardians, and significant family members should be actively engaged in discussions and workshops about the importance of higher education. Strengthening family support can positively influence students' motivation, reinforce educational aspirations, and create a supportive environment for pursuing college or alternative training programs.
- 5. Strengthen Institutional Support for Academic Preparedness.** Schools should provide programs that enhance students' study skills, time management, resilience, and ability to handle academic and personal demands. Mentorship, peer support groups, and preparatory courses can help students develop confidence and a sense of control over their college readiness.
- 6. Improve Accessibility and Logistical Support.** Practical support such as transportation assistance, digital learning platforms, satellite learning centers, and

flexible class schedules can help students overcome geographical and logistical barriers, ensuring that distance or travel constraints do not limit access to higher education.

- 7. Support Students Balancing Family and Work Responsibilities.** Flexible learning programs, part-time courses, or evening classes can enable students to continue their education while meeting family obligations or earning income. Schools should also provide guidance on time management strategies to help students balance these responsibilities effectively.
- 8. Foster Motivation and Positive Perceptions of Education.** Schools should implement programs that reinforce the value of education, connect learning to personal and career goals, and highlight success stories. By strengthening students' internal motivation and emphasizing the tangible benefits of higher education, schools can help students sustain long-term commitment to their goals.
- 9. Develop Holistic Decision-Making Skills.** Programs that focus on problem-solving, goal setting, and critical thinking can empower students to make informed choices about their futures. This can include workshops, simulations, and career-planning activities that help students evaluate options realistically and select pathways that best suit their skills and circumstances.

These recommendations aim to create a comprehensive, student-centered support system addressing financial, social, academic, and personal challenges. By implementing these strategies, schools can help students transition successfully from Senior High School to higher education or alternative career paths, ensuring that their aspirations are matched with practical opportunities and realistic support.

Plans for Dissemination and Utilization

DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES	Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Month 4	Month 5
1. Presenting the results of the study and proposed school-based interventions to the school research coordinator.					
2. Sharing the findings and recommendations with Senior High School faculty for integration into guidance and career orientation programs.					
3. Presenting the results and suggested interventions to the District Education Office to inform policy and support programs.					
4. Submission and presentation of the study results and proposed intervention plan in the Division Research Conference.					

5. Conducting a workshop for parents and community stakeholders on supporting students' college aspirations and understanding barriers to higher education.					
6. Dissemination of a summarized research report and recommendations to local education policymakers and school boards for potential policy adoption.					

Compliance with Ethical Consideration

The study strictly adhered to established ethical standards to ensure the protection of the rights, privacy, and welfare of all participants. Prior to conducting the research, permission was secured from the school authorities of San Isidro Senior High School. The purpose and procedures of the study were clearly explained to the participants, and their informed consent was obtained before data collection. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and respondents were free to withdraw from the research at any time without consequences. To maintain confidentiality and anonymity, no identifying personal information was collected from the participants. All responses were treated with strict confidentiality and were used solely for academic and research purposes. Furthermore, the collected data were securely stored and accessed only by the researcher to prevent unauthorized use. These ethical measures ensured that the research process respected the participants' rights, upheld their dignity, and maintained the integrity of the study.

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